

GUIDELINES for PARTICIPATION IN MOOT COURT

Author: **Kumushkhon Abdumutalimova** is a student of Tashkent State University of Law, participant of several international moot courts (Willian Vis, Children Rights MootCourt, Ph.C. Jessup). During participation in Ph.C. Jessup competition her team succeeded Top – 10 in International Preliminary rounds around the world, Top – 32 in the final scoring, setting record for teams from Central Asia.

The content of the guidelines. Each prestigious law school throughout the world incorporates in their curriculum program participation in different moot courts. The branch of law of moot courts competitions can vary, starting from international law and ending with national law system. In the history of moot courts one of the firsts was Ph.C. Jessup moot court competition in the field of international public law. Nowadays, there are variety of moot court competitions in a different branches of law. The present guidelines will provide a universal formula for beginners to succeed in participation in moot courts for each stage.

Advantages and disadvantages of participating in moot courts. Every participant of moot courts takes their own advantage from participating in moot courts, however, there are common ones that each student shares.

Firstly, moot court competition is a time consuming process, which can take a full academic year or even more.

Secondly, participating in a moot court can have a negative impact on a person's mental health. This problem is often faced in circumstances such a poor time management or depending on the difficulty of the given case.

Thirdly, while participating in moot court, a student has to forget about other educational activities, including writing articles or even attending university's classes.

Despite the fact that there can be a wide range of disadvantages, the positive sides prevail. For instance, during moot court process, participants learn to make a proper legal analysis, draft official documents, build logically structured argumentation. One the most obvious advantage is to gain experience of oral presentations before the judges. It is a well-known fact that a professional and good lawyer must have excellent oral skills in order to convenience the audience. Thus, participation in moot courts is a real chance to develop it. If you wish to enhance those skills, participating in moot courts competition is right for you! Now let's discover what is essential for participating in moot courts competitions.

Preparation stage. What must be done? Most moot courts have seasonal basis, thus it is possible to take some times for preparation process for about 1-3 months. This is a list of what is recommended to do for preparation:

1. Enrich your basic knowledge in the branch of law related to the moot court. When you have already made a choice in which moot court competition you will take a part, it is necessary to have basic knowledge in this field. Remember, the given cases usually include very specific topics, thus in order to resolve the issue effectively, the basic knowledge must be present.

2. Do pre-research work on a specific topic, if they are available. If you are sure that you have plenty basic knowledge in the branch of law of the competition, then it is time to do a more specific research. Usually, moot court organizers announce the topics, which will concern the case. Thus, before the release

of the case, participants have a chance to make research on specific topics. This will help you to familiarize and deal with the case effectively in a shorter period of time.

3. Improve a legal drafting skills.

Since the first stage of every moot court is submission of written work, having good drafting skills as essential. Therefore, while doing research on a specific topic, make sure to use legal terms and construct the argumentation in a logical order. The legal drafting skill cannot be acquired in a short period of time. In preparation process work on this, however, this skill can be acquired during participation itself.

The above listed steps are essential for the preparation process, if you wish to succeed in moot court you are participating. One might argue that those steps can be during the process itself, however, since the participation is a time consuming process, there is a low possibility to improve general knowledge in law.

The next step is the release of the case - Once the case of the competition is released it is time to choose the side!

The first step after the release of the case is to read the problem several times. For the first reading do not circle, highlight anything. The first reading is devoted for overall understanding the problem, to identify existing issues and related topics. After understanding the problem, it is time for team work.

The most important thing after the case release is a discussion with team member. First, teammates can make a plan of actions. Also, discussion helps to figure out, which team member is good at understanding of a specific issue. Usually, after the discussion takes a specific issue or a side on which they will work and draft memorials.

Working on the issue. Before making structure of the argumentation, a particular time must be allocated for research. This is moot court competition; therefore, the given

situation is itself problematic in theory. Thus, in a doctrinal work there must some discussion on a particular position. Thus, it is not recommended to hurry on

making arguments. First, make a proper research then make argumentation, covering all sides of the question.

Legal drafting skills. Legal drafting is a fundamental skill that every lawyer must master to succeed in profession. Crafting precise and effective legal documents is crucial for getting high scores. In this comprehensive guide, we will explore how to improve legal drafting by providing steps to improve.

5 Steps for Legal drafting skills

Step №1: Familiarize with the rules of the moot court.

Each moot court competition has its own requirements on the form and proper citation to the references etc. Remember, the form of the written work is scored as well as substance.

Step №2: Utilize educational resources.

If there are available resources on Best Memorials of the previous years, make sure to read them and analyze the structure, using of the legal terms. While reading the articles, take note of their style, tone, and techniques that you can incorporate into your own writing.

Step №3: Be clear and concise.

Clarity and conciseness are paramount in the journey of improving your legal drafting skills:

- Simplify complex sentences and eliminate unnecessary repetitions.

- Utilize straightforward and accessible language to convey your message effectively.
- Minimize the use of technical terms.
- Vary sentence length for enhanced readability.
- Craft your writing with consideration for your target readers, adopting a tone that captivates their attention.
- Tailor your writing style to be informative, decisive, persuasive, or descriptive, depending on the purpose and audience.

Step №4: Maintain a professional tone

- Use active voice to make your writing more dynamic and impactful.
- Capture their attention with an informative, decisive, persuasive, or descriptive tone based on the purpose and audience.
- Observe their style, tone, and techniques for inspiration to enhance your own legal drafting.
- Infuse uncommon terminology to add originality and depth to your writing.
- Strike a balance between professionalism and engaging language to keep readers interested.
- Keep sentences concise and clear, conveying complex ideas effectively.
- Present arguments confidently and persuasively while staying respectful and courteous.
- Seek feedback from peers or mentors to fine-tune your tone and style.
- Continuously refine your legal drafting skills by learning from experienced writers.

Step №5: Proper citation

Citations lend credibility and authority to your legal drafts, backing up your arguments with relevant sources.

- Use a recognized citation style, depending on the legal field and audience.
- Refer to primary legal sources like statutes, regulations, and case law to strengthen your legal arguments.
- For comprehensive support, include secondary sources like legal treatises, law review articles, and academic publications.
- Ensure accurate and consistent formatting of citations throughout your document.
- Cross-reference citations with footnotes or endnotes for easy navigation and verification.
- Integrate parallel citations for multiple references to the same legal authority.
- Be meticulous in verifying and updating your citations to maintain accuracy and reliability.
- Prioritize using recent and authoritative sources to bolster your legal analysis.
- Review and edit citations carefully to avoid errors and maintain professionalism in your legal drafting.
- Keep practicing and refining your writing style for continuous improvement.

Oral Presentations. The most responsible moment of every moot court competition is orally presenting of the arguments before the judges. Here are some technical tips for oral presentations:

1. Write a script of the speech. It is not necessary to learn it by heart, but a script will help to construct the arguments.
2. A script of the speech itself must consist the following parts:
 - Introduction

- Body part
- Conclusion.

In the introduction part you familiarize the judges with a roadmap, which must be clear and precise. The body part includes presenting the arguments themselves: Argument #1, Argument #2 etc. Remember, arguments must be presented in IRAC format:

I – issue R – rule

A – application C – conclusion.

In conclusion part, you briefly summarize the said arguments and please the Court. Rules of addressing the court. Depending on the moot court, the oralist must address the members of judges with the words such Your Excellency, Mr./Madam President, Mr./Madam Arbitrator etc. Make sure to keep eye contact with each member of the judging committee. Answer to their questions precisely in a polite manner. Remember, the final scores of the oral pleadings depend not only on the substance of the speech, but also on the form, which include the manner you address the court, the tone and the speed of the speech. Find your own style of the oral presentations. Also, it is recommended to watch the presentations of the lawyers or other moot court participants, who gained high scores.

Good luck in further preparations and participation in moot courts!